

Review

COVID-19 Pandemic: Challenges to Oral Physician and Future of Dentistry

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Abstract

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This article aims to provide a brief overview of origin, epidemiology, causative agent, common sign and symptoms, and route of transmission of COVID-19. Besides challenges to oral physicians and providing comprehensive guidelines and protocols of international health care institutions for managing dental patients during and after pandemic. In 21st century so far COVID-19 is the most robust and most crucial global public health challenge to the world community. It has influenced every aspect of life and every profession worldwide directly or indirectly. It was first discovered in Wuhan, China in Dec 2019.¹ Initially, the disease was epidemic in China but unfortunately rapidly spread globally, resulting in COVID-19 Pandemic 2020, as announced by WHO Director-General, Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus on March 11, 2020.² It is a viral disease caused by a virus, now known as the severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2 (SARS-COV-2). Health care professionals, especially oral physicians, are exposed to a higher risk of getting infected with COVID-19 due to close contact with infected patients and with droplets and aerosols generated during routine dental clinical procedures. Due to dentistry's unique characteristics and a higher risk of transmission of COVID-19 in dental community, oral physicians are imperative to follow exclusive guidelines and protocols to prevent the disease. We identified relevant articles to date using a manual library search, journal publications on the subject, and critically reviewed them.

Keywords: COVID-19, Challenges, Dentistry, Oral Physician, Pandemic, WHO

INTRODUCTION

WHO defines a pandemic as “a worldwide spread of a new disease.” It is called COVID-19 by World Health Organization (WHO) because (CO) stands for Corona; (VI) Virus; (D) Disease; and (19)2019 the year that the virus first hit.³ COVID19 remains the most crucial global public health challenge for the world community, influencing every aspect of life and every profession worldwide directly or indirectly. It has triggered severe socio-economic, political, environmental, and health crises.

Origin of COVID-19

It was first discovered in Wuhan, China, in Dec 2019. Initially, the disease was epidemic in China but unfortunately rapidly spread globally, resulting in COVID-19 Pandemic 2020, as announced by WHO Director-General, Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus on March 11, 2020. The first case of corona disease in Pakistan was confirmed on 26 February, 2020, when a student in Karachi tested positive upon returning from Iran⁴.

Figure 1. An illustration of various possible transmission routes of COVID-19.⁷

Epidemiology of COVID-19

Globally, as of 3:05 pm CEST, 2 July, 2020 there have been 10, 53 3,779 confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 512,824 deaths, reported to WHO.⁵ It has affected 216 countries including Pakistan. There are 217,809 confirmed cases of COVID-19 in Pakistan, including 4,473 deaths so far.

Causative agent of COVID -19

COVID-19 is a viral disease caused by a virus now known as the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona virus 2(SARS-COV-2).⁶

Modes of transmission of COVID-19

COVID-19 is commonly transmitted from person to person via hands, saliva, nasal droplets and surface contacts. It is a respiratory infection and can be transmitted through droplets of different sizes. When the droplet particles are >5-10µm in diameter, they are referred to as respiratory droplets, and when they are <5µm in diameter, they are referred to as droplet nuclei.⁸ The air-droplet transmission occurs when a person is in close contact (within 1m) with someone who has respiratory symptoms (e.g., coughing or sneezing).

Therefore, the individual is at risk of having the oral or nasal mucosa or the conjunctiva (eyes) exposed to infective respiratory droplets. Transmission may also occur through fomites (objects or materials which are likely to carry infection, such as clothes, utensils, and furniture) in the immediate environment around the infected person. It can occur by direct contact (hand shaking) with infected person and indirect contact with surfaces in the immediate environment or with objects used on the infected person (e.g., mouth mirror, hand piece, dental forceps).

Figure 1 shows various possible transmission routes of respiratory infection between an infected and a susceptible individual. Both close range (i.e. conversational) airborne transmission and longer range (over several meters) transmission routes are illustrated here. The orange head color represents a source and the white head color a potential recipient (with the bottom right panel indicating that both heads are potential recipients via self-inoculation from contaminated surface fomite sources). Here 'Expiration' also includes normal breathing exhalation, as well as coughing and/or sneezing airflows. Airborne droplets can then settle on surfaces (fomites) from where they can be touched and carried on hands leading to further self-inoculation routes of transmission.

Common sign and symptoms

The infected person usually presents with upper respi-

Figure 2. Shows common signs and symptoms of COVID-19.⁸

ratory tract infection (RTI) and complains of high-grade fever, a dry cough and shortness of breath.

opportunistic bacterial infections.

7. Analgesics/Anti-inflammatory (NSAIDs).

Diagnosis and Treatment

The diagnosis of COVID-19 can be based on a combination of epidemiological information (e.g., a history of travel to or residence in affected region 14 days before symptom onset), clinical signs and symptoms, chest X-ray or CT imaging findings and laboratory tests (e.g., reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction [RT-PCR] tests on respiratory tract specimen collected from nasal or throat swabs.⁹

Treatment

COVID-19 is a new chapter to the medical world. There is currently no treatment explicitly approved for corona disease. Medical researchers are trying to find a comprehensive treatment and vaccination for COVID-19. The following experimental and supportive treatments have been tested to see how effective they are.

1. Antiviral or retroviral medications.
2. Breathing support, such as mechanical ventilation.
3. Steroids to reduce lungs swelling.
4. Blood plasma transfusions.
5. Routine anticoagulation Enoxaparine –Low dose heparin etc.
6. Routine Antibiotics like Azithromycin for treatment of

Challenges to oral physician

Healthcare professionals, especially oral physicians, are exposed to a higher risk of getting infected with COVID-19 due to close contact with infected patients and with droplets and aerosols generated during routine dental clinical procedures.¹²

The New York Times Magazine published an article entitled “The Workers Who Face the Greatest Corona Virus” on March 15, 2020, dentists to be on the highest risk levels of COVID-19 contamination.

Comprehensive guide lines and protocols for managing dental patients during and after COVID-19 pandemic

Due to the particular characteristics of dentistry and higher risk of transmission of COVID-19 in dental community, oral physicians are imperative to follow unique guidelines and protocols to prevent the disease.

Emergency vs. None Emergency Dental Procedures

The American Dental Association (ADA) provided full guidelines on March 18 to consider dental emergencies

Figure 3a: Shows throat swab for RT-PCR.¹⁰

Figure 3b: Shows nasal swab for RT-PCR.¹¹

Figure 3c. CT-chest of COVID-19 patient, showing multiple cotton-like patches density in peripheral of both lungs.¹²

Figure 3d. Shows typical COVID-19 chest x-ray versus normal. The image on the right shows multiple - focal patchy airspace opacities.¹³

Figure 4. An illustration of COVID-19 transmission routes in dental clinics and hospitals.¹⁴

Figure 5. Shows workers who face the most significant corona virus risk.¹⁵

and nonemergency dental care as part of an effort to restrain the spread of the COVID-19 and lessen the burden on hospital and emergency department.

According to the ADA, "are potentially life-threatening and require immediate treatment to stop ongoing tissue bleeding [or to] alleviate severe pain or infection". Also, dentists should use their professional judgment in determining a patient's need for urgent or emergency care. Table 1

Patient Pre-Visit screening via Teledentistry

During COVID-19 Pandemic it has been necessary to rethink many conventional ways of working in dentistry. It is a right time to introduce Teledentistry in our dental hospitals and setups. The initial screening via telephone

or video call to identify patients with suspected or possible COVID-19 infection can be performed remotely at time of scheduling appointments. During this outbreak, targeted screening questions for COVID-19 must be asked. These questions should include the following:

1. Do you have fever or experience fever within the past 14 days?
2. Have you experienced a recent onset of respiratory problems e.g., a cough or difficulty in breathing within the past 14 days?
3. Any recent travelling history to an area with high incidence of COVID-19?
4. Have you come into contact with a patient with confirmed COVID-19 infection within the past 14 day?
5. Have you recently participated in any gatherings, meetings and weddings within the past 14 days?

Essential vs. Non-Essential Dental Procedures					
This guide is to help dentists identify which dental procedures are considered Essential vs. Non-Essential during a national emergency. Dentists are to use the below as a guide, and encouraged to make professional judgement calls on the urgency of any procedure during emergencies. Patients with non-essential needs should be encouraged to maintain oral hygiene practices to maintain their current status. Please note: All procedures should also consider risk factors associated with demographics more susceptible to COVID-19, such as elderly patients and those with underlying health conditions.					
Specialty	Procedure Type	Essential	Non-Essential		
Restorative	Low to Moderate Risk of Decay	Fillings/Restorations/SSC			
		Incipient to MId Decay		X	
		Moderate Decay	X		
		Severe Decay	X		
		Fracture tooth repair			
		Pain	X		
	No Pain (if patient feels uncomfortable ,consider that patient in pain)		X		
	Crown				
	Crowns to be completed to navigate completion of care for moderate-severe decay as well as to complete RCT	X			
	Proactive replacement of restoration without decay		X		
	Veneers			X	
	Pediatric and High Risk of Decay	Fillings/Restorations/SSC			
		Incipient to MId Decay	X		
		Moderate Decay	X		
Severe Decay		X			
Fracture tooth repair					
Pain		X			
No Pain (if patient feels uncomfortable ,consider that patient in pain)		X			
Crown					
Crowns to be completed to navigate completion of care for moderate-severe decay as well as to complete RCT	X				
Proactive replacement of restoration without decay		X			
Cosmetics	Cosmetic Procedures		X		
Endodontics	Active Infection	X			
	Patient in Pain	X			
	Swelling or cellulitis	X			
Emergency Patients	Any patient who is contacting the practice with urgent needs should be seen to decrease overflow to Emergency Departments	X			
Hygiene	Prophy (low risk)		X		
	Prophy (high risk)	X			
Use of scalers are encouraged. Use of cavetron at Dr. discretion.					
Exams and X-Rays	Performing exams as usual to screen and determine patient category and needs	X			
Preventative	Sealants		X		
Oral Surgery	Implants		X		
	Extractions				
	Active Infection	X			
	Patient in Pain	X			
	Swelling or cellulitis	X			
Third Molar without the above symptoms		X			
Orthodontics	Ortho Procedures				
	New Bandings		X		
	Patient complications (wire or bracket fractures)	X			
	Recal		X		
	Debond*		X		
Doctor to make judgement on if recal has extended time period and warrants a visit.					
Periodontics	Initial Therapy SRP or Maintenance				
	Patient has additional risk factors (Diabetes, Cardiac disease)	X			
	No additional risk factors		X		
Use of scalers are encouraged. Use of cavetron at Dr. discretion.					
Prosthodontics	Bridges		X		
Pediatrics	Dentures and Removables		X		
	Follow guidelines above for specific procedures				

Table 1. An illustration of the ADA of Essential Vs. None Essential Dental Procedures.¹⁶

A positive response to any of the 5 questions should raise initial concern. The None Emergency dental procedures should be deferred for at least 2 weeks. These patients should be encouraged to engage in self – quarantine and contact with their primary care physician by telephone.

Patient Evaluation and Cohorting in Dental Clinics

The oral physician must be able to identify a suspected case of COVID-19. Upon patient arrival in dental practice, the body temperature of the patient should be measured in the first place using a contact-free forehead digital

Table 2. An overview of patient screening and management for COVID-19 in dental office.¹⁷

thermometer. Dentist should take a through medical history. Patients who present with fever ($>100.4^{\circ}\text{F}=38^{\circ}\text{C}$) and/or respiratory disease symptoms should have elective dental care deferred for at least 2 weeks. Also, individuals with suspected COVID-19 infection should be seated in a separate, well - ventilated waiting area at least 6ft unaffected patients seeking dental care. Patients should be requested to wear a surgical mask and follow proper respiratory hygiene, such as covering mouth and nose before coughing and sneezing.

Pharmacological Management

In suspected or confirmed cases of COVID-19 infections requiring urgent dental care for conditions such as tooth pain and/or swelling, pharmacological management in the form of antibiotic and/or analgesics is an alternative. This approach may offer symptomatic relief and will provide dentists sufficient time to either refer the patient to a specialist or deliver dental care with appropriate measures in place to prevent the spread of infection.

Specific Recommendations during emergency dental care

In the unlikely event of providing dental care to suspected or confirmed cases of COVID-19 infection, dentists are

imperative to follow the below recommendations.

Personal protective equipment

During dental procedures, the spread of oral microorganisms mostly radiates towards the dentist's face, particularly in the inner part of the eyes and around the nose, which are important areas for infection transmission. Personal Protective Equipments (PPE) can form an effective barrier against most hazards of aerosols generated from the operative site.

Hand hygiene

Hands have a crucial role in the transmission of COVID-19. SARS-COV-2 primarily spreads through droplet and contact transmission. Contact transmission means by touching infected people and/or contaminated objects or surfaces. Thus, our hands can spread the virus to other surfaces or our mouth, nose or eyes if we touch them. Hand hygiene is one of the necessary and most effective measures that we can take to reduce the spread of COVID-19. The WHO global hand hygiene campaign Save Lives: Clean Your Hands- on 5, May, 2020 mobilize people around the world to increase adherence to hand hygiene in health care facilities, thus protect health care workers and patients from COVID-19. Figure 7

1. Face shield; 2. Goggles/Glasses; 3. Surgical gowns;
4. Head cover; 5. Mask; 6. Respirators; 7. Shoe cover

Figure 6. Shows different types PPE.¹⁸

Your 5 Moments for Hand Hygiene

- 1** BEFORE TOUCHING A PATIENT
- 2** BEFORE CLEAN / ASEPTIC PROCEDURE
- 3** AFTER BODY FLUID EXPOSURE RISK
- 4** AFTER TOUCHING A PATIENT
- 5** AFTER TOUCHING PATIENT SURROUNDINGS

Figure 7. Shows 5 moments of hand hygiene for health professionals.¹⁹

Pre-procedural mouth rinse

Pre-procedural mouth rinse is one of the most effective methods of reducing the proportion of microorganisms in oral aerosols. The effect of chlorhexidine, which is commonly used for pre-procedural mouth washing in dental practice, has not yet been demonstrated to be capable of eliminating 2019nCoV. However, oxidative agents containing mouth rinses with 1% hydrogen peroxide or 0.2% povidone-iodine are recommended.

Use Disposable Devices

Use of disposable (single-use) devices such as mouth mirror, syringes to prevent cross contamination.

Radiographs

Extra oral imaging such as panoramic radiography (OPG)

or cone-beam computed tomographic (CBT) imaging should be used to avoid gag or cough reflex that may occur with intra oral imaging.

Rubber dam isolation

Dentists should use a rubber dam to minimize splatter generation. Using rubber dam creates a barrier in the oral cavity that effectively reduces the generation of droplets and aerosol mixed with patient saliva and/or blood. It may be advantageous to place the rubber dam so that covers the nose.

Devices Not to be Used

Dentists should minimize the use of ultrasonic instruments, high-speed hand pieces, and 3-way syringes to reduce the risk of generating contaminated aerosols.

Figure 8. shows rubber dam isolation.²⁰

Figure 9. Shows extra oral suction machine.²¹

Extra Oral Aerosol Suction Machine

Extra-oral suction system provides a practical and effective solution to mitigate the risk posed by aerosols by quickly removing and filtering them. It suction away aerosols generated by dental procedures and protect clinical teams and patients from the spread of harmful bacteria and viruses generated from aerosols.

Anti retraction hand piece

Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of a dental hand pieces that do not have an anti-retraction function should be avoided. For emergency treatment, anti-retraction hand pieces designed with anti-retroactive valves can play an effective role in preventing the diffusion and dispersion of droplets and aerosols.

Environmental surface disinfection

During aerosol generating procedures, droplets containing infective pathogens could be deposited on the surrounding surfaces. Surface disinfectants which contain 62%71% ethanol, 0.5% hydrogen peroxide, and 0.1 % (1 g/L) sodium hypochlorite are highly recommended.

Clinical Waste Management

The clinical waste generated after treatment of COVID-19 positive patients is as dangerous and infectious as that of hepatitis B and C or AIDS. All reusable instruments should be pre-treated, cleaned, sterilized and properly stored. None- reusable items should be stored in clinical waste bags within a designated area. The surface of the package bags should be marked and disposed according

Figure 10. Shows anti-retroactive high speed hand piece.²²

Figure 11. An illustration of dental office disinfection.²³

Figure 12. Show clinical waste management.²⁴

to the local regulations.

CONCLUSION

COVID -19 has significantly affected dentistry. After announcing COVID-19 as pandemic by the WHO, the New York Times Magazine published an article ranking the health professions at the highest risk of COVID-19 infection, amongst which dental professionals occupied the top of the ranking. Dentists should limit their dental care to only emergency cases and utilized appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) to minimize the risk of transmission during emergency dental treatments. The current situation suggests that the costs of providing dental treatment may increase in the future. Mainly because of several reasons including the need for additional resources such as PPE, dental practice modifications, and waiting times due to the need for segregation of patients in the waiting areas resulting in a reduced number of patients that can be seen daily. After COVID-19 Pandemic, there is a general fear of visiting dentists among the public. Consequently, demand for elective dental treatment can decrease, and the patient may choose emergency extraction over preservative treatment such as root canal treatment. On the other hand, to avoid and prevent the dental problem, some patients will pay more attention to their oral and dental health by improving their oral hygiene. Due to the overall economic impact of COVID-19, extended lockdown measures, and closure of dental surgeries, it is predicted that there can be further uncertainty for the dentist, reduced income, and more job loss in the future. COVID-19 pandemic may encourage the use of digital intraoral scanners instead of conventional impressions and may increase the demand for computer-aided design and manufacturing (CAD/CAM) and 3D-printing technology.

Funding

This editorial work received no special funding

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors want to acknowledge the MRMMJS Editorial Office and all the anonymous Reviewers.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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